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Steps Involved in Utilising a Scriptural Review Research Method as a Tool for Explaining Biblical Research Problems

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Abstract

Biblical research studies, as a new discipline, has not been accorded the required priority and recognition in our theological institutions. This recognition is important to avoid using the traditional scientific research methods to explaining pneumatic problems. Biblical research is not only epistemological but also theological and spiritual. Thus, using the current traditional secular scientific tools to explain biblical research problems may culminate in research conflict and failure that will endanger biblical research studies. Therefore, this paper explores the utilisation of scriptural review research method as a tool for explaining and analysing biblical research problems. The methodology adopted is sola scriptura methodology, a research methodology that is based on Scripture alone. The study discusses the biblical foundation for scriptural review, employing Jesus model and the need for this method in biblical research studies. The research outlines the steps involved in conducting scriptural review research, which include defining the research problem, seeking the face of God, conducting a scriptural review, developing a research question, selecting relevant scriptural texts, analysing and interpreting scriptural texts, synthesising findings, drawing conclusions, validating findings, communicating results, and reflecting and refining the research process. In addition, the work explains validity and reliability of biblical data and addresses their internal and external criticisms. The study concludes that only the scriptural review research method has the potential to address biblical problems when all types of investigation have failed to produce the desired results.

Keywords: *scriptural review research method, biblical research Problems, sola scriptura research methodology, the Bible, God.*

1.0 Introduction

A scripture review¹ in biblical research studies is a systematic, purposeful and pneumatic examination and analysis of relevant biblical passages to gain a better and deeper understanding of their meanings, contexts, and significance (Dele Alaba Ilesanmi, 2025). Scriptural review is a vital tool in biblical research studies because it brings a deeper understanding and correct interpretation of God's word through the help of the Holy Spirit. It is contingent on the Holy Spirit. Without the Holy Spirit, our biblical hermeneutics and exegesis are useless. Biblical research problems require divine solutions and often require a nuanced understanding of Scripture by the help of the Holy Spirit.

Scriptura review research method is a tool to gain access to the mysteries of God, learning about and know Him better. It is a truth-finding and problem-solving exercise. It may seem dreary and difficult exercise if researchers are not given proper orientations. Indeed, the best way to study the Scripture is to be in spirit. We are to worship God in spirit and in truth (John 4:23-24).² Since God is a Spirit (John 4:24), His Word must be approached in spirit and in truth because it is only when we align our spirit with His that we can get to know Him better (Matt 16:17). Revelation of God's Word can only be made possible by God Himself. Jesus asserts that flesh and blood cannot reveal the mysteries of God:

When Jesus came into the coasts of Caesarea Philippi, he asked his disciples, saying, Whom do men say that I the Son of man am? And they said, Some say that thou art John the Baptist: some, Elias; and others, Jeremias, or one of the prophets. He saith unto them, But whom say ye that I am? And Simon Peter answered and said, Thou art the Christ, the Son of the living God. And Jesus answered

¹ In the work titled, "The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review" in *Mature Journal*: 2025. Ilesanmi, Dele A explains in great details the need for biblical review in biblical research studies. The author made this bold step as the first person to write on this to create a paradigm shift from traditional literature review to scriptural review.

² All scriptural citations are from the King James Version of the Bible, unless otherwise stated.

and said unto him, Blessed art thou, Simon Barjona: for flesh and blood hath not revealed it unto thee, but my Father which is in heaven (Matt 16:13-17).

Hence, scriptural review research method is pneumatic. It is not scientific; it is not philosophical; but, it is spiritual. Therefore, adopting scientific methods to solve spiritual problems will culminate in multiple problems that will affect the spiritual life of man.

Ilesanmi (2024) says that Biblical research should be of interest not only to the academics but to all Christian professionals, church leaders, ministers and workers, theological institutions, and anyone who seeks true knowledge and wants to keep the knowledge fresh and up-to-date. It is important to note that Biblical research is a complex and multidimensional field that requires a range of methodologies or approaches. Although biblical research problems often require a nuanced and multidisciplinary approach, integrating insights from theology, history, philosophy, science, and other relevant fields, these approaches must align with scriptural methods. Scriptural review research methods offer a systematic, purposeful, and rigorous approach to studying biblical texts, enabling researchers to gain a deeper understanding of the scripture and its application to contemporary contexts pneumatically³ or pneumagogically.⁴

One important method in Biblical Research Studies is the Scriptural Review Research Method, which involves a systematic analysis of relevant scriptural texts to gain insights and explanations for research problems. Ilesanmi (2024, 2025) asserts that Biblical Research is conducted with a purpose to: (1) discover divine truth, (2) establish the divine truth, (3) uncover the revealed hidden truth of God, (4) increase our knowledge and deepen our understanding of God and the universe He created, (5) obey divine order of being diligent to studying the word, (6) expand the frontiers of biblical and theological knowledge, among others.

Thus, the study explores the utilisation of scriptural review method as a tool for explaining biblical research problems. The author believes that scriptural review method broadens our knowledge and deepen our understanding of the world around us and the world

³ “Pneumatically” means “spiritually.”

⁴ “Pneumagogically” also means “spiritually”. It means the teaching that occurs under the influence of the Holy Spirit. See Ilesanmi’s “Pneumagogy: A Proposed Theory for Effective teaching and Learning in Biblical Christian Education” for a comprehensive understanding.

beyond us. The method provides a comprehensive approach to conducting scriptural reviews, analysing relevant texts, and applying findings to research problems. The paper highlights the importance of scriptural review methods in biblical research and demonstrates their effectiveness in providing insights and explanations for complex research problems.

2.0 Rationale for Sola Scriptura Research Methodology

This paper adopts a sola scriptura research methodology to explore the utilisation of scriptural review methods in explaining biblical research problems. A *sola scriptura methodology* is a research methodology that is based on Scripture alone. The phrase *sola scriptura* is from the Latin words. The word *sola* means “alone,” “ground,” or “base,” and the word *scriptura* means “writings”—referring to the Scriptures. Therefore, combining the two words, *sola scriptura* means “by Scripture alone,”⁵ that is, Scripture alone is authoritative for the doctrine, faith and practice of the Christian Church. Indeed, the Bible is complete, authoritative, inerrant, infallible, and true. “All scripture is given by inspiration of God, and is profitable for doctrine, for reproof, for correction, for instruction in righteousness: That the man of God may be perfect, thoroughly furnished unto all good works” (2 Tim 3:16–17). Scripture is the alone source of divine revelation. Therefore, this author believes that using this methodology is the only way to avoid subjectivity and keep personal opinion from taking priority over the teaching of the Bible – the authoritative Word of God – the only solid and reliable basis for doctrine, faith, and practice. “Sola scriptura holds not only to the primacy of Scripture but to the sufficiency of Scripture as the “only” supreme authority in all matters concerning the church. All truth necessary for one’s salvation and Christian life is taught explicitly or implicitly in Scripture.”⁶ We are forbidden to exceed what is written in Scripture”: “Now, brothers and sisters, I have applied these things to myself and Apollos for your benefit, so that you may learn from us the meaning of the saying, “Do not go beyond what is

⁵ Check the title, “What is sola scriptura?” in <https://www.gotquestions.org/sola-scriptura.html>, for a better understanding

⁶ Check here: <https://www.gotquestions.org/prima-scriptura.html>

written.” Then you will not be puffed up in being a follower of one of us over against the other” (1 Cor 4: 6 NIV). It is therefore believed that by adopting a Sola Scriptura research methodology help to emphasise the authority of Scripture in addressing research issues.

The rationale behind or assumption underlying sola scriptura approach are as follows:

1. To recognise the Bible as the ultimate authority in matters of doctrine, faith and practice.
2. To ensure that research aligns with biblical principles and doctrine.
3. To promote objectivity and rigour in biblical research.
4. To avoid subjectivity and keep personal opinion from taking priority over the teaching of the Bible.
5. The Bible is sufficient, that is, it contains all necessary information for understanding God's will and purposes for humanity.
6. The Bible is the only reliable source of information and revelation for the understanding of human and societal problems.

3.0 Biblical Foundation and Jesus Model

The biblical foundation for scriptural review method can be seen in several principles and practices in the Bible. To review means to study, to examine, to analyse, or to evaluate. The review is important to establish the truth in God’s word concerning certain situations. There is no situation that does not require biblical or scriptural interpretation. Hence, scriptural review is key to biblical research studies, which includes biblical studies, theological studies, biblical Christian education, and all other disciplines that hold the Bible as the primary source of their contents and information, and the ultimate authority in all matters of faith, doctrine, theory, and practice. It is a divine order and principle that biblical Christian believers must study, search, or review the Scripture to understand the intention of God (Proverbs 2:3-5; Rom 12:2; 2 Peter 1:20-21).

Scriptural review is predicated on the word of God that:

- Believers should seek understanding and insight into God's Word (Ps 119:169).
- Believers should renew their mind through the word to know the mind or will of God concerning those (Rom 12:2)
- Scriptural review involves searching for wisdom and knowledge of God (Prov 2:3-5).
- Scriptural review helps recognise the limitations of human understanding and the superiority of God's thoughts and ways (Isaiah 55:8-9).
- Through scriptural review, believers will be given God's way of thinking – 1 Corinthians 2:16: "But we have the mind of Christ.
- Scriptural review helps believers to avoid shame and correctly apply the word of God (2Tim 2:15).
- The Berean model gives more convincing support to scriptural review to establish the truth (Acts 17:11)
- Scriptural review requires diligence study of the word (2 Timothy 2:15).
- Scripture study aims to understand God's intention and meaning (2 Peter 1:20-21).
- Scriptural review involves meditation on Scripture to deepen understanding and application (Psalm 119:15-16).

Jesus Model

What is more, the use of scriptural review method is important to provide solution to problems, which is the essence of biblical research, and it is also rooted in Scripture. For examples, Jesus' use of Scripture to respond to temptation of Satan (Matthew 4:1-11) – the enemy, an antagonist – shows the importance of scriptural review and how relevant it is to apologetics; Jesus adopted Scriptures to teach people

of His time (Luke 24:25-27); the apostles also used Scripture to teach and argue with others (Acts 17:2-3, Romans 1:1-4). Jesus frequently referenced and used scripture in the Bible, particularly from the Old Testament to prove His points. There many instances where Jesus used scripture. A few of them are listed here for our understanding:

Temptation in the Wilderness

1. Matthew 4:4; Luke 4:4 – "But he answered and said, It is written, Man shall not live by bread alone, but by every word that proceedeth out of the mouth of God. Jesus cited Deuteronomy 8:3 - "And he humbled thee, and suffered thee to hunger, and fed thee with manna, which thou knewest not, neither did thy fathers know; that he might make thee know that man doth not live by bread only, but by every word that proceedeth out of the mouth of the Lord doth man live."
2. Matthew 4:7; Luke 4:12 – "Jesus said unto him, It is written again, Thou shalt not tempt the Lord thy God." Jesus cited Deuteronomy 6:16 – "Ye shall not tempt the Lord your God, as ye tempted him in Massah."
3. Matthew 4:10; Luke 4:8 – "Then saith Jesus unto him, Get thee behind me, Satan: for it is written, Thou shalt worship the Lord thy God, and him only shalt thou serve." Jesus quoted Deuteronomy 6:13 – "Thou shalt fear the Lord thy God, and serve him, and shalt swear by his name."

Teaching and Preaching

Jesus often referenced Scripture to illustrate His teaching:

1. Matthew 21:42; Mark 12:10-11; Luke 20:17 – "Jesus saith unto them, Did ye never read in the scriptures, The stone which the builders rejected, the same is become the head of the corner: this is the Lord's doing, and it is marvellous in our eyes?" citing Psalm 118:22-23

– "The stone which the builders refused is become the head stone of the corner. This was the Lord's doing, and it is marvellous in our eyes."

2. Matthew 21:13; Mark 11:17; Luke 19: 46 – "And said unto them, It is written, My house shall be called the house of prayer; but ye have made it a den of thieves." Jesus cited Isaiah 56:7 – "Even them will I bring to my holy mountain, and make them joyful in my house of prayer: their burnt offerings and their sacrifices shall be accepted upon mine altar; for mine house shall be called an house of prayer for all people."

3. Matthew 21:13; Mark 11:17; Luke 19: 46 - "And he taught, saying unto them, Is it not written, My house shall be called of all nations the house of prayer? but ye have made it a den of thieves." Jesus cited Jeremiah 7:11 – "Is this house, which is called by my name, become a den of robbers in your eyes? Behold, even I have seen it, saith the Lord."

Debates with Pharisees and Sadducees

Jesus used Scripture to respond to His critics – the antagonists

1. Matthew 22:31- 32; Mark 12: 26-27; Luke 20: 37-38 – "But as touching the resurrection of the dead, have ye not read that which was spoken unto you by God, saying, "I am the God of Abraham, and the God of Isaac, and the God of Jacob? God is not the God of the dead, but of the living." Jesus quoted Exodus 3:6 – "And he said, I am the God of thy father, the God of Abraham, the God of Isaac, and the God of Jacob. And Moses hid his face; for he was afraid to look upon God."

2. Matthew 22:44; Mark 12:36; Luke 20:42-43 – "The Lord said unto my Lord, Sit thou on my right hand, till I make thine enemies thy footstool?" Here, Jesus was citing Psalm 110:1 – "The Lord said unto my Lord, Sit thou at my right hand, until I make thine enemies thy footstool."

Other instances

1. John 10:34 – "Jesus answered them, Is it not written in your law, I said, Ye are gods?" He cited Psalm 82:6 – "I have said, Ye are gods; and all of you are children of the most High."

2. Matthew 12:3-4 (KJV) - "But he said unto them, Have ye not read what David did, when he was an hungred, and they that were with him; How he entered into the house of God, and did eat the shewbread, which was not lawful for him to eat, neither for them which were with him, but only for the priests?" citing 1Samuel 21: 1-6 "... So the priest gave him hallowed bread: for there was no bread there but the shewbread, that was taken from before the LORD, to put hot bread in the day when it was taken away."

To facilitate understanding about Jesus’ model of scriptural review method, the above is tabulated thus:

S/N		New Testament	Jesus Cited Old Testament	Mark
1	Temptation in the Wilderness	Matthew 4:4; Luke 4:4	Deuteronomy 8:3	Relevant
		Matthew 4:7; Luke 4:12	Deuteronomy 6:16	Relevant
		Matthew 4:10, Luke 4:8	Deuteronomy 6:13	Relevant
2	Teaching and Preaching	Matthew 21:42; Mark 12:10-11; Luke 20:17	Psalm 118:22-23	Relevant
		Matthew 21:13; Mark 11:17; Luke 19:46)	Isaiah 56:7	Relevant
		Matthew 21:13; Mark 11:17; Luke 19:46)	Jeremiah 7:11	Relevant

3	Debates with Pharisees and Sadducees	Matthew 22:32; Mark 12:26-27; Luke 20:37-38)	Exodus 3:6	Relevant
		Matthew 22:44; Mark 12:36; Luke 20:42-43	Psalms 110:1	Relevant
4	Other Instances	John 10:34	Psalms 82:6	Relevant
		Matthew 12:3-4	1 Samuel 21:1-6	Relevant

The table shows a few examples of Jesus using scripture in the Bible. His use of scripture demonstrates His knowledge and understanding of the Hebrew Bible and its relevance to His teachings. This espouses Ilesanmi's proposition in his recent work titled, *The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review*.⁷ The author posits that scriptural review is essential for accurate biblical interpretation, theological understanding, and effective scholarly writing in biblical research studies. The researcher further asserts that review of relevant scriptural texts in biblical research is to ensure the accuracy, depth, and relevance of biblical scholarly findings. Scriptural review method is essential to:

1. Uphold the authority and sufficiency of Scripture in scholarly writings, especially in biblical research studies, and, ensuring that God's Word remains central in the life of the church (2 Timothy 3:16-17).
2. Teach theological truths
3. Respond to challenges
4. Guide decision-making

⁷ This work argued for the utilisation of scriptural review as against the traditional literature review in biblical research studies and related fields. The paper was published in Mature Journal, 2025.

5. Demonstrate fulfilment of prophecy
6. Understand the Scripture
7. Promote scriptural literacy and research
8. Obey divine mandate
9. Rightly divide the word of truth
10. Defend the truth one knows about God's Word – to make an apologia or to apologise.
11. Enrich scholarly argument and work in biblical and theological education.

4.0 The Need for Scriptural (Biblical) Review Research Method (SRRM)

Biblical or Scriptural research is important in all disciplines, especially biblical research studies. It involves all aspects of human life: spiritual, religious, moral, educational, scientific, political, economic, social, cultural, historical, etc. Indeed, biblical studies, theological studies, biblical educational studies, and, especially biblical research studies – the umbrella name for all research works that use the Bible – have to be well understood by biblical scholars if they are to put their theories and research in appropriate contexts. Generally, **Scriptural Review Research Method** helps to utilise 2 Timothy 3:16-17 because the entirety of God's Word is truth (Psalm 119:160). To get the truth and solution to your problem, you must search the Scripture – the Bible. The Bible is the magazine of life. Research conducted on the premise of human theories, philosophies, or ideologies without the support of the Word of God cannot be regarded as quality or truth. Therefore, we stand by the truth because God's Word is truth (John 1:17; 14:6; 17:17; 8:32; Eph 4:21; cf. Ps 12:6; 19:7-9; 119:9, 11, 104, 151–152, 160). 'For we can do nothing against the truth, but for the truth' (2 Cor 13:8).

The following are the argument for the necessity of scriptural review method:

1. *Accurate Interpretation with the help of the Holy Spirit:* Scriptural review method ensures accurate interpretation of scripture. It helps researchers understand the biblical context, literary structure, and historical background, leading to more accurate interpretation. For example, "Knowing this first that no prophecy of the scripture is of any private interpretation. For the prophecy came not in old time by the will of man: but holy men of God spake as they were moved by the Holy Ghost." (2 Pet 1:20-21).
2. *Understanding Context:* Scriptural review method considers the context of scripture. For example, "So they read in the book in the law of God distinctly, and gave the sense, and caused them to understand the reading" (Neh 8:8).
3. *Avoiding Misinterpretation:* Scriptural review method helps biblical scholars and believers avoid misinterpretation of scripture. For example, "Jesus answered and said unto them, Ye do err, not knowing the scriptures, nor the power of God" (Matt 22:29). This text underscores the importance of scriptural review. People make mistakes because they do not know, examine the Scripture very well.
4. *Discerning Truth:* Scriptural review method enables discernment of truth from error. For example, the Bible says "Prove all things; hold fast that which is good." (1Thess 5:21). "Beloved, believe not every spirit, but try the spirits whether they are of God: because many false prophets are gone out into the world." (1 John 4).
5. *Deepening Understanding:* By examining relevant scriptures, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of theological concepts, themes, and doctrines. Scriptural review method deepens understanding of God's word. "Open thou mine eyes, that I may behold wondrous things out of thy law" (Ps 119:18). God is involved when His word is involved.
6. *Applying Scripture:* Scriptural review method facilitates application of scripture to life. "But be ye doers of the word, and not hearers only, deceiving your own selves." (Jam 1:22) Utilisation of scriptural review method will enhance the correct application of God's word, even to our lives.
7. *Teaching and Preaching:* Scriptural review method is essential for teaching and preaching. 2 Timothy 2:15) – "Study to shew thyself approved unto God, a workman that needeth not to be ashamed, rightly dividing the word of truth" (cf 2Tim 3:16-17)

8. Spiritual Growth: Scriptural review method promotes spiritual growth by deepening one's understanding of God's word. For example, "As newborn babes, desire the sincere milk of the word that ye may grow thereby." (1 Peter 2:2); "But grow in grace, and in the knowledge of our Lord and Saviour Jesus Christ." (2 Peter 3:18).

9. Scriptural review provides wisdom and guide for living a godly life. "Thy word is a lamp unto my feet, and a light unto my path." (Ps 119:105).

10. Effective Pastoral Ministry: A scriptural review informs pastoral ministry, enabling pastors to provide effective guidance, care, and discipleship (2 Tim 3:16-17).

5.0 Steps Involved in Utilising Scriptural Review Research Method

Although the steps involved in performing scriptural review research are quite similar to other types of research, the pneumatic nature of this research makes it unique.

Scriptural Review Research Cycle/Process

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Step 1: Define the Research Problem

The researcher should identify the specific biblical research problem or question that needs to be addressed, ensuring that it is focused and answerable. It is important for biblical research scholar to formulate a feasible, well-articulated problem area to explore. A well-defined research problem area is a critical step in utilising scriptural review research methods.

Step 2: Seek the face of God

For a biblical researcher to effectively communicate the message or word of God, the Author of the message or word must be involved. If God is not involved, His word cannot be effectively and correctly interpreted and communicated. Hence, biblical researchers must involve God in their scholarly work in prayers. The Holy Spirit, the Spirit of God, who teaches us all things cannot be ignored in our biblical scholarly research (John 14:26). The researchers need to seek God first concerning their research before they embark on it (Matt 6:33). Biblical researchers need Pray for illumination, requesting God's illumination of Scripture (Ephesians 1:17-18).

Step 3: Conduct a Scriptural Review or Tripartite (Triangulation) Review

Conducting a scriptural review is essential in scriptural review research. Review, according to Ilesanmi (2025) can be divided into three types, which the researcher calls *tripartite review or triangulation review*: (1) Scriptural review; (2) Christian literature review; and (3) Extra-Biblical or Scriptural review. One major review that a biblical researcher cannot ignore is scriptural review. Next important to scriptural review is Christian review. Extra-biblical review, which is traditionally regarded as literature review is the opinion of secular scholars that may not hold water in biblical research studies. The Bible is enough to give meaning to life by proffering lasting solutions to human problems. The Bible is the only reliable source of knowledge and truth. Thus, this step is essential in a biblical scholarly research work. Therefore, researchers must review relevant biblical texts on the topic at hand or that pertain to the research problem,

identifying gaps in existing research works and look for areas for further exploration. Reviewing existing research and scholarly works related to the research problem is important. Hence, the Ilesanmi's Tripartite (Triangulation) Review can be adopted.

Step 4: Develop a Research Question

Developing research questions or hypotheses is a crucial step in scriptural review research. Researchers must formulate specific and focused questions that guide the research process. Without a research question, our biblical review research can become little or more than aimless gathering of facts. There must be a problem to solve. This problem will bring about a question that will make our review research process to be focused.

Step 5: Select Relevant Scriptural Texts to collect your Data

Selecting relevant scriptural texts is a critical step in scriptural review research. This is a data collection process. The researcher must consult the Creator's Manual, the Bible, for data collection. The Bible is not only the records of the past but also of the present and future. It is a timeless Magazine of life that has answers to all human problems. Researchers must identify biblical passages that are relevant to the research question or problem, considering context, genre, and authorship. Any data collected here are valid and reliable because they represent God's voice.

Step 6: Analyse and Interpret Scriptural Texts

Analysing and interpreting scriptural texts is a key step in scriptural review research that must not be taken lightly by researchers. Researchers must employ exegetical methods, such as historical-grammatical or literary analysis, to gain a deeper understanding of the biblical text. Before analysing the selected scriptural texts using various methods, such as exegesis, hermeneutics, and contextual analysis, involve the Holy Spirit to guide you to speak God's mind and avoid personal bias.

Step 7: Synthesise Findings

Synthesising findings is an essential step in scriptural review research. Researchers must integrate insights from multiple passages consulted and reviewed, identifying patterns, themes, and relationships. This will help researchers to provide insights and explanations for the research problem.

Step 8: Draw Conclusions

Drawing conclusions is a critical stage in scriptural review research. Researchers must answer the research question, discussing implications for biblical understanding and application.

Step 9: Validate Findings

Validation is not an issue in biblical research studies because the aim of the biblical researcher is for dependability. This is what the Bible has met thousands of years ago. Thus, validating findings is an important step in scriptural review research. Researchers must compare their findings with existing research, taking into consideration the biblical foundation and implications of every research work and its results.

Step 10: Communicate Results

Communicating results is a vital step in scriptural review research. Researchers must write a clear and concise report, sharing their findings with relevant audiences. The Bible has encouraged us to share our light since we are the light of the world (Matt 5:14-15) – share this light (i.e., faith, testimony, and good works) with others, rather than hiding it. The researchers can publish their findings in both local and international journals, websites, and social media.

Step 11: Reflect and Refine

Reflecting and refining the research process is an essential step in scriptural review research. Researchers must reflect on the research process and refine their methods for future research.

6.0 Validity and Reliability of Biblical Data

The major aims of biblical researchers are to establish the truth in God's word to solve human and societal problems, draw more people closer to their Maker, and advance the frontiers of knowledge in biblical research studies. These aims can only be achieved when the source of our data is dependable. Dependability is reflected in validity and reliability. Biblical researchers base their research on the biblical principles of pursuit of truth: "Buy the truth, and do not sell it" (Prov 23:23); pursuit of integrity: "The integrity of the upright guides them" (Prov 11:3); pursuit of accurate interpretation: "Knowing this first of all, that no prophecy of Scripture comes from someone's own interpretation" (2 Pet 1:20); and pursuit of total reliance on God's Spirit for accurate interpretation of God's word (John 16:13; 1 Cor 2:10-14) because every word of God is tested and proved true (Prov 30:5); and the entirety of God's word is truth (Ps 119:160); and God exalts His word more than anything else (Ps 138:2). Thus, the role of biblical researchers is to place premium on God's word than human opinions and scientific evidence that are not in consonance with the word of God. They are to refute and destroy any arguments, speculations, theories, ideas, or reasoning that contradict the word and knowledge of God (1 Cor 10:5). Indeed, divine inspiration and universal applicability, historical accuracy, as confirmed by archaeological and historical evidence, and consistency of the Bible from Genesis to Revelation have established the validity and reliability of biblical data.

Furthermore, scriptural cross-referencing, which involves examining multiple passages on a topic, analysing connection or relationship between these passages to establish the truth. The Bible says "The facts of every case must be established by the testimony of two or three witnesses" (2 Cor 13:1 NLT), supporting triangulation review. Scripture's Cross-Reference enhances the validation and reliability of biblical data. Sources are checked against each other or one another. As a general rule in biblical research studies, whenever a citation

or quotation from another source appears in a book or article, the researcher should find the original quotation to check it against two criteria, namely:

- i. What is its context? And
- ii. Is it accurately stated?

Jesus model, as exemplified above, adds more credence to Scriptural Cross-Referencing.

6.1 Validity

Having established the unassailable validity and reliability of God's word, validity in biblical research studies refers to the extent to which a study accurately measures or interprets the biblical text, concepts, or phenomena being investigated. It involves ensuring that the research methods and findings are grounded in the biblical text and its context. Validity in biblical research can also mean the accuracy and truthfulness of the research findings. It involves ensuring that the research measures what it claims to measure and that the conclusions drawn are supported by the data.

6.2 Types of Validity

1. Internal validity: Refers to the extent to which the research design and methods accurately measure the phenomenon being studied without systematic errors or biases. The researcher is expected to use appropriate research methodology. Seeking guidance from others: Consulting with other believers and scholars in the same discipline to gain a deeper understanding of Scripture (Prov 11:14). In biblical research, internal validity ensures that:

1. Research design accurately captures the biblical concept or phenomenon.

2. Methods of data collection are appropriate and unbiased.

3. Analysis is rigorous and accurate

2. *External validity*: Refers to the extent to which the research findings can be generalised to other contexts, populations, or situations. The word of God has universal applicability – it can be applied in all situation (2 Tim 3:16-17). Thus, the biblical researchers should use the Bible as the primary source of their data in their research is to meet the universal acceptability. It is important to note that biblical researchers do not rely on external interpretation of Scripture. The Scripture is sufficient enough to interpret itself. The researchers are to use Scripture to interpret Scripture. In other words, rather than relying on external sources. In other words, external sources cannot give understanding to people except the Scripture interpret itself (Psalm 119:130).

In biblical research, external validity considers the following, among others:

1. Relevance: Research findings should be relevant or applicable to varied contexts.

2. Generalisability: The extent to which researcher's findings applicable to other populations.

3. Transferability: The usefulness of the researcher's findings in different settings.

6.3.0 Reliability

Reliability in biblical research studies refers to the consistency and dependability of the research findings. It involves ensuring that the research methods and results can be replicated or verified by other researchers. Consistency is one of the characteristics of the Bible: "Jesus Christ is the same yesterday and today and forever" (Heb 13:8). This highlights unchanging nature of God (Mal 3:8). His word

is unchangeable, providing timeless truth, inspiring unwavering trust, and offering enduring guidance (Ps 119:89; Isa 40:8; Heb 6:17). Thus, the unchangeable nature of God's word lends more credence to its reliability.

2. Dependability: "Let your yes be yes, and your no, no" (Matthew 5:37), emphasising consistency.

6.3.1 Types of Reliability

1. *Inter-rater reliability*: Refers to the consistency of measurements or interpretations between different researchers or raters. Despite over 40 different authors, the biblical message is cohesive (2 Tim 3:16-17; 1 Pet 1:2:20-21). Therefore, biblical researchers or scholars can come to similar conclusions about Scriptural meaning through the help of the Holy Spirit, who guides all believers to truth (1 Cor 2:10-16; John 2: 20-22).

2. *Intra-rater reliability*: Refers to the consistency of measurements or interpretations by the same researcher or rater over time. Reliability is ensured when researcher's yes is yes, and no, is no, any time, any day, the truth is established in God's word, and anything outside this is not from God (Matthew 5:37).

6.4 Ensuring Validity and Reliability

To ensure validity and reliability in biblical research studies, researchers must learn to rely absolutely on the Holy Spirit in the interpretation of biblical data and they should not rely on their hermeneutic and exegetical understanding (Prov 3:5). To ensure validity and reliability in their work, the biblical researchers are to:

- i. Recognise the Holy Spirit's guidance in understanding God's Word (John 16:13);
- ii. Allow the Holy Spirit to guide interpretation, rather than relying merely on human reasoning (1 Corinthians 2:10-14);

- iii. Do scriptural cross-referencing, which involves examining multiple passages on a topic – triangulation citation or reference – and analysing connection between passages. "Every matter must be established by the testimony of two or three witnesses" (2 Corinthians 13:1), supporting triangulation. Aside ensuring validity and reliability, biblical researchers can gain a better and richer understanding of biblical teachings by cross-referencing Scripture. Scripture's Cross-Reference enhances the validation and reliability of biblical data.
- iv. Consider sending their work for peer review and critique by scholars in the same field (Proverbs 11:14);
- v. Use rigorous exegetical methods; and
- vi. Consider the historical, cultural, and literary context of the biblical text.

It is crucial to note that by prioritising validity and reliability, biblical researchers can produce high-quality, trustworthy research that contributes to a deeper understanding of scripture and can increase the credibility and applicability of their findings.

6.5 Importance of Validity and Reliability

Validity and reliability are essential in biblical research studies because they:

1. Ensure accurate interpretation of scripture.
2. Build trust in research findings.
3. Foster credible and dependable research.
4. Inform sound decision-making and application.

7.0 Internal Criticism

Internal criticism occurs when it is certain that the documents are either originals or as close to originals as one can get. It evaluates the meaning, truth, and believability of the statements in the document. For example, the biblical researchers or scholars question whether a writer's representation of biblical principles is biased. It may also be appropriate to ask if the author of a document was in a position to make a valid report of a biblical principle or event or occurrence, or whether the writer is competent as a recorder of fact.

7.1 External Criticism

You cannot defend what you do not experience or know. Though external criticism is concerned basically with the authenticity or genuineness of the data, biblical data are reliable and genuine. External criticism does not change the truth in God's word. No record has value for the study unless it is genuine. Biblical data are words of God that have been tested millions of times and the result remains the same. The Bible is available and accessible for criticism. It is open to feedback and critique. In other words, it is willing to receive feedback and critique from others. Indeed, the Bible is the only "sacred" book that has submitted itself to both external and internal investigations and criticisms, and to scientific and philosophical inquiry. The truth will always remain the truth. The truth in God's word can only be understood by those who are spiritual because the spiritual things cannot be evaluated or assessed by unspiritual critics (1 Cor 2:10-16).

8.0 Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the effectiveness of a scriptural review research method, informed by Sola Scriptura principles, in addressing biblical research problems. The steps involved in the use of scriptural review research have shown some sense of the potential power inherent in the method. Indeed, only the scriptural review research has the potential to address biblical problems when all types of investigation have failed to produce the desired results. Scriptural review research methods offer a systematic, purposeful, pneumatic,

and rigorous approach to studying biblical texts. By following the steps outlined in this paper, it is believed that researchers can effectively utilise scriptural review research method to gain a deeper understanding of biblical texts and address complex research problems. This paper also contributes to the field of biblical research studies, providing a framework for conducting scriptural review research, highlighting the validity and reliability of biblical data and addressing their external and internal criticisms. Therefore, the author believes that, by adopting a sola scriptura research methodology, this study will enhance the authority of Scripture in addressing research issues and the only way to avoid subjectivity and keep personal opinion from taking priority over the teaching of the Bible.

References

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